

THE FORMATION OF EDUCATIONAL MOTIVATION AT SCHOOL AGE IS ONE OF THE CENTRAL PROBLEMS OF MODERN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Abstract. *We examined the concept of “Learning motivation”, which acts as a particular type of general motivation, an integral part of which is motives.*

Having studied the psychological and pedagogical literature, we have established that motives associated with the educational process are divided into cognitive motives associated with the content of educational activity and the process of its implementation and social motives associated with various social interactions of the student with other people. That is why the key figure in the formation of educational motivation is not only the teacher, but also the child’s parents, so it is important to make them your allies in this matter, otherwise the teacher’s attempts to resolve this issue will be minimized.

Key words: *Formation, motivation, psychology, pedagogy, education, training, education, technology.*

In the modern educational environment of primary schools, already from the first grade, the problem of increasing the effectiveness of teaching is quite acute. First of all, this is due to the fact that the amount of information that primary schoolchildren must learn is growing year by year, and this is precisely where the problem of forming educational motivation arises, because, as you know, in order to absorb knowledge and learn to apply it in life, it is necessary desire and activity. Therefore, primary school teachers face a primary task, which is to find methods and forms that would help students not only in mastering knowledge, but would turn the educational process into an exciting process of cognition.

It is known that a younger student’s positive or negative attitude toward learning can be the reason for his success or failure. Therefore, in our opinion, the search for new approaches to further improving the content, forms and methods of teaching in order to have a positive impact on the formation of educational motivation in younger schoolchildren is fully justified.

Learning motivation is defined as a particular type of motivation included in learning activities, that is, learning motivation is the motivated activity exhibited by students in achieving learning goals [2].

Like any other type, educational motivation is determined by a number of factors specific to this activity. Firstly, it is determined by the educational system itself, the educational institution where educational activities are carried out, secondly, by the organization of the educational process, and thirdly, by the subjective characteristics of the student [3].

A.K. Markova defines the educational motive as “... the student’s focus on certain aspects of educational work, associated with the student’s internal attitude towards it” [13].

In psychological and pedagogical literature, all motives are traditionally divided into two large groups:

1. Cognitive motives associated with the content of educational activities and the process of its implementation;

Social motives associated with various social interactions of the student with other people.

The study and formation of learning motivation must be objective, on the one hand, and carried out in a humane manner, respectful of the student's personality, on the other. Forming educational motivation does not mean putting ready-made motives and goals into the student's head, but putting him in such conditions and situations of activity development, where the desired motives and goals would take shape and develop taking into account and in the context of past experience, individuality, and internal aspirations of the student himself. .

The same learning activity can have different meanings for different students. This, in general terms, determines their motivation for learning. Identifying the motivation for learning and its meaning for the student in each specific case plays a decisive role in the teacher's determination of educational measures. Thus, we can say that when approaching the formation of educational motivation in the classroom, you first need to study the individual characteristics of each student, and then, based on the data obtained, select methods for developing motivation.

N. F. Talyzina believes that the initial task for a primary school teacher is, on the one hand, to bring to the student's consciousness those motives that are socially insignificant, but have a fairly high level of effectiveness. For example, the desire to get good grades. Students need to be helped to understand the objective connection of assessment with the level of skills and knowledge. And in this way, gradually approach motivation, which is associated with the desire to have a high level of skills and knowledge. This, in turn, should be recognized by students as a necessary condition for their successful activities useful to society. On the other hand, it is necessary to increase the effectiveness of motives that are perceived by students as significant, but do not actually influence their behavior. This way of forming learning motivation is directly related to the peculiarities of the organization of the educational process [3].

Various motives can serve as motivation for educational activities, such as:

1. cognitive (interest in mastering new knowledge, desire to perform tasks of increased difficulty, self-education, etc.);
2. social (usefulness in the future, authority among classmates, and so on);
3. disciplinary (school routine, position of parents and teachers, punishment of parents and disapproval of classmates).

The teacher must always understand whether students have an interest in learning and whether they are motivated to gain new knowledge. To do this, you can use a variety of questionnaires that will make it clear whether the child is committed to the learning process or whether he needs to be led to this in some way, motivated.

Such methods will allow the teacher to identify problems of motivation and select the right ways to eliminate these problems and increase the cognitive activity of students, which is understood as the selective focus of the individual on objects and phenomena of the surrounding reality.

When forming cognitive activity, the leading tasks of the teacher are:

1. showing attention to each child;
2. the ability to see and notice in a student the slightest spark of interest in any aspect of educational work;

3. creating conditions to ignite this spark and turn it into a genuine interest in knowledge and science.

In many ways, the formation of positive learning motivation depends not only on the teacher. Basic human needs, primarily social and cognitive, are laid down and actively develop in the early periods of childhood. Therefore, in order to form and increase the educational motivation of his students, the teacher must work not only with children, but also with parents.

From the first days of working with the class, it is necessary to organize conversations, which should be an integral part of parent-teacher meetings, give methodological recommendations to parents, and involve a psychologist in solving this problem. The work of parents to develop positive educational motivation in children aged 6-7 years in a family environment should be aimed at ensuring that the child finds himself in a single educational environment at school and in the family.

Organizing joint activities between the teacher and the family will contribute to the formation of a positive attitude of younger schoolchildren towards learning. The family must understand the enormous importance of education for the present and future child. Only such work will help put into practice the formula: "The success of a child's education lies in the successful cooperation of the teacher and parents."

The teacher should help parents collaborate with their children to achieve a common goal - the formation of positive learning motivation. Parents must explain to the child why he needs to go to school and not just study, but study well.

It is also important that parents study with the child at home, help him with homework, and check the completion of additional tasks. It is necessary to remind parents that they, too, should encourage the child's success; this is another incentive for children to strive for better results.

Parents must be immediately warned that there will be no immediate positive results. There is no need to demand more from a child than he can, because only systematic work can give any results.

Thus, we can say with confidence that to increase educational motivation, family and school must work together; only by working as a team can a positive result be achieved. Just as one family, without a school, cannot educate its child, a school, without a family, cannot do this.

To understand the concept of "Learning motivation", it is very important to separate the concepts of "Motivation" and "Interest". By "Motivation" we mean incentives that cause the activity of the body and determine its direction [6].

Interest (from Latin "to have meaning, to be important") is an emotional state associated with the implementation of cognitive activity and characterized by the incentive of this activity [8].

Cognitive interest is expressed primarily in the student's emotional attitude to the subject of study. L.S. Vygotsky writes: "Interest is, as it were, a natural driver of child behavior; it is a true expression of instinctive striving, an indication that the child's activity coincides with his organic needs. The pedagogical law says: before you want to call a child to any activity, interest him in it, take care to discover that he is ready for this activity, that he has exerted all the forces necessary for it, and that the child will act himself, the teacher can only manage and direct his activities" [13]. Thus, we can say that the formation of interest in educational activities is one of the components in the formation of educational motivation of a primary school student.

Analysis of the literature allowed us to conclude that the same educational activity can have different meanings for different students, so the teacher must first study the individual characteristics of each of his students, and then, based on the data obtained, select ways to form motivation.

But, since the teacher works with a large group of students, he needs to know not only the individual personal characteristics of each of his students, but also the characteristic features of primary school age in implementing the tasks of forming positive educational motivation; this will be the subject of the next paragraph of our diploma research.

The National Curriculum defines the development of the child's personality as a priority task, which requires the teacher to have a new approach to organizing the learning process.

The lesson, as it was before, remains the main unit of the educational process, but the functionality of the teacher and the main activities of students are fundamentally changing. The main task of the teacher is to help students master knowledge; he should only guide them in finding answers to questions.

The priority in the lesson is the independent work of primary school students; the main approaches to organizing activities are practical and activity-based approaches. Thus, the teacher's task in the lesson is to guide the actions of children, and not to transfer ready-made knowledge to them.

A modern lesson should be problematic in nature, starting with goal setting. The problem of the lesson is formed by the students themselves under the guidance of the teacher. It is necessary to discuss different points of view on solving the problem, find a common way to solve it by building a logical chain, and lead students to the significance of the knowledge they receive and the ability to apply it in practice.

According to the National Curriculum in the modern educational process of primary school, the following types and types of lessons are distinguished:

1. A lesson in discovering new knowledge, acquiring new skills.

Goals:

Activity-based: teach children new ways of finding knowledge, introduce new concepts and terms.

Content-based: form a system of new concepts, expand students' knowledge by including new definitions, terms, and descriptions.

Lesson structure for discovering new knowledge, acquiring new skills and abilities:

1. motivational stage;
2. stage of updating knowledge on the proposed topic and carrying out the first trial action;
3. identifying the difficulty: what is the complexity of the new material, what exactly creates the problem, searching for contradictions;
4. development of a project, a plan to get out of the existing difficulty, consideration of many options, search for an optimal solution;
5. implementation of the chosen plan to resolve the difficulty. This is the main stage of the lesson, at which the "discovery" of new knowledge occurs;
6. primary consolidation of new knowledge;
7. independent work and testing according to the standard;
8. inclusion of knowledge and skills in the system;

9. reflection, which includes reflection on educational activities, self-analysis, and reflection of feelings and emotions.

2. Reflection lesson

Goals:

Activity-based: to develop in students the ability for correctional-control type reflection, to teach children to find the cause of their difficulties, to independently build an algorithm of actions to eliminate difficulties, to teach self-analysis of actions and ways to find a resolution to the conflict.

Content-based: consolidate acquired knowledge, concepts, methods of action and adjust if necessary.

Reflection lesson structure:

1. motivational stage;
2. updating knowledge and implementing primary action;
3. identifying individual difficulties and implementing new knowledge and skills;
4. building a plan to resolve the difficulties that have arisen (searching for ways to solve the problem, choosing optimal actions, planning work, developing a strategy);
5. implementation in practice of the chosen plan, strategy for resolving the problem;
6. generalization of identified difficulties;
7. carrying out independent work and self-testing using a reference sample;
8. inclusion of knowledge and skills in the system;
9. implementation of reflection;

In the structure of a reflection lesson, the fourth and fifth stages can be repeated depending on the complexity of the identified difficulties and their abundance.

Systematization of knowledge (general methodological orientation)

Goals:

Activity-based: teach students how to structure acquired knowledge, develop the ability to move from the particular to the general and vice versa, teach them to see each new knowledge, and repeat the learned method of action within the entire topic studied.

Content-based: teach generalization, develop the ability to make theoretical assumptions about the further development of the topic, teach the vision of new knowledge in the structure of the general course, its connection with already acquired experience and its significance for subsequent learning.

Structure of knowledge systematization:

1. self-determination;
 2. updating knowledge and recording difficulties;
 3. setting the educational task, lesson goals;
 4. drawing up a plan and strategy to resolve the difficulty;
 5. implementation of the selected project;
 6. stage of independent work with verification against a standard;
 7. stage of reflection of activity;
- ## 4. Developmental control lesson

Goals:

Activity-based: teach students methods of self-control and mutual control, develop abilities that allow them to exercise control.

Content-based: testing knowledge, skills, acquired skills and self-testing of the student.

Developmental control lesson structure:

1. motivational stage;
2. updating knowledge and implementing a trial action;
3. fixing local difficulties;
4. creating a plan to solve the problem;
5. implementation of the chosen plan in practice;
6. generalization of types of difficulties;
7. carrying out independent work and self-testing using a reference sample;
8. solving creative problems;
9. reflection of activity.

Having analyzed the types and content of each stage of the structure of a modern lesson, it should be noted that the very understanding of the lesson, as part of the educational process, is fully aimed at developing the student as an active subject of his cognitive activity, which creates all the conditions for the formation of positive motivation for the learning process already in itself, and the task of a modern primary school teacher is to effectively use a variety of forms, methods and techniques of student work in the classroom, one of which is a didactic game[4].

Having studied the psychological and pedagogical literature on this issue, we can confidently say that the key figure in the formation of educational motivation is not only the teacher, but also the child's parents. We also concluded that before beginning the formation of educational motivation in primary school children, the teacher needs to study not only the individual characteristics of each of his students, he needs to know the characteristic and typological features of primary school age.

As part of our diploma research, we studied the concept of "Junior school age". This is a stage in the development of a child that corresponds to the period of his education in primary school. The chronological boundaries of this age are different for different countries and differ depending on a number of factors, therefore, in order to form positive learning motivation, the teacher needs to create such conditions in the lessons in which the younger student will strive to gain knowledge, that is, lessons, first of all, should be bright, emotional and rich.

We have revealed the concept of "Lesson" and determined that it remains the basic unit of the modern educational process, but the functionality of the teacher and the main activities of students are fundamentally changing.

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